

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES
SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

EPILEPTIC SEIZURE: A SHORT REVIEW

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Abstract:

The neurobiological, cognitive, psychological, and social repercussions of seizure recurrences, as well as an enduring (i.e., persistent) propensity to produce seizures that is not triggered by any acute central nervous system damage, are the hallmarks of epilepsy, a chronic brain disorder. Globally, epilepsy affects people of all ages and genders. A thorough summary of the pathophysiology, clinical signs, diagnostic standards, and treatment approaches of epilepsy is given in this article. Current antiepileptic medications are effective in 60–70% of patients and reduce seizures without changing the underlying propensity to produce seizures. The causes of epilepsy include immunological, metabolic, and viral variables as well as structural and genetic disorders of the brain. In order to determine the cause and categorize the type of seizure, EEG, imaging, and laboratory testing are used to support the largely clinical diagnosis of epilepsy. AEDs are the first-line treatment for epilepsy; refractory patients are treated with surgery, neuromodulation, or dietary changes.

Keywords : Epilepsy , Hypersynchronous neuronal firing , Oxidative stress , Treatment

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Please cite this article in **press** Varsha V et al., **Epileptic Seizure: A Short Review**, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2025; 12(09).

INTRODUCTION:

Recurrent, spontaneous seizures caused by excessive electrical discharges in brain neurons are the hallmark of epilepsy (1). Seizures may be localized (using a small network of neurons) or generalized (using a rapidly activated bilaterally scattered neural network) (2). About 40% of epilepsy cases have a known cause, such as ischemic stroke, traumatic brain injury, intracerebral hemorrhage, infections of the central nervous system, brain tumors, various neurodegenerative diseases, and prolonged acute symptomatic seizures like status epilepticus (SE) or complex febrile seizures. In connection with epilepsy, glutamate and γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) are the two neurotransmitters that have been thoroughly investigated. In epileptic events, the glutamatergic and GABAergic systems are both essential. An imbalance between glutamate-mediated excitation and GABA-mediated inhibition has been proposed as the cause of neuronal hyperexcitability in epilepsy (3). There are numerous choices for treating epilepsy with new antiepileptic medications, each with its own modes of action and adverse effect profiles. With a wide range of activity, few side effects, and few drug interactions, the new antiepileptic medications are well tolerated (4).

TYPES OF EPILEPSY

In 1989, the International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) created a classification system for epilepsy and epileptic syndrome. The epilepsies were classified as focal or generalized based on their symptoms (5).

ETHIOLOGY

If there are concordant electroclinical tests and/or clinical results, an aberrant neuroimaging finding can be reasonably inferred to be the origin of the patient's seizures. This is known as a structural etiology. If a known or suspected specific disease-causing mutation in a gene or copy number variant with seizures as a common phenotype exists, then epilepsy is thought to have a genetic basis. CNS infections are the most prevalent recognized cause of epilepsy in several parts of the world and a significant risk factor for the condition. An infectious etiology describes a patient who has epilepsy rather than seizures brought on by an acute central nervous system infection. According to the theory, seizures are a primary sign of metabolic epilepsy, which is thought to be caused by a known or suspected metabolic disturbance (6).

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

The pathophysiology of different epileptic syndromes has been demonstrated to vary, although they appear to have traits associated to ictogenesis in common, such as enhanced neuronal excitability and synchronization (7). Ictogenesis and epileptogenesis

have long been thought to result from an imbalance between excitation and inhibition. GABA and glutamate, the brain's main inhibitory neurotransmitters, should ideally be in balance. Seizures may arise from an overexcited central nervous system brought on by insufficient GABA and/or excess glutamate (8,9,10). Evidence suggests that the development and course of epilepsy may be influenced by neuronal hyperexcitability and oxidative damage brought on by an excess of free radicals (11). Changes in ROS, RNS, and nitric oxide (NO) signaling pathways have been linked to oxidative stress; bioavailable NO is reduced, while ROS and RNS production is elevated. Inflammatory reactions trigger oxidative and nitrosative stress pathways, which in turn produce highly reactive free radical molecules through subsequent mitochondrial metabolic activities. Seizures and neuronal death are related to mitochondrial malfunction and oxidative stress. In several animal seizure models, there is evidence that antioxidant therapy may lessen damages brought on by oxidative free radicals (12).

TREATMENT OF EPILEPSY

Pharmacological treatment: The main way that antiepileptic medications (AEDs) work is by prioritizing inhibition over excitement, which stops or stops seizure activity from starting or spreading. Based on their primary mode of action, the AEDs can be categorized. GABA enhancement (benzodiazepines and barbiturates), GABA reuptake inhibition (valproic acid, gabapentin, tiagabine), blocking of glutamate (lamotrigine, felbamate, perampanel), inhibition of voltage-gated Ca^{2+} channels (phenytoin), inhibition of Na-dependent action potentials (e.g., phenytoin, carbamazepine, lamotrigine, topiramate, zonisamide, lacosamide, cenobamate), inhibition of voltage-gated Ca^{2+} channels (phenytoin), and opening of potassium channels (ezogabine) are some of the mechanisms. Ethosuximide and valproic acid, two medications used to treat absence seizures, most likely work by blocking T-type Ca^{2+} channels in thalamic neurons (13).

Neurosurgical treatment: the evolution of neurosurgical methods for treating epilepsy, starting with the introduction of temporal lobe surgery and the influence of electroencephalography (EEG). As a laboratory technique for identifying epileptic diseases and locating focal epileptogenic abnormalities, EEG represents the most significant advancement in the development of contemporary surgical treatment for epilepsy (14).

Neurostimulation : When surgery is not an option for patients with drug-resistant epilepsy, neurostimulatory treatments are palliative measures. Potential seizure formation or propagation can be prevented by applying electrical impulses to

particular brain regions or peripheral nerves. In open-label, uncontrolled studies, two of the most popular neurostimulation methods—deep brain stimulation (DBS), which uses electrodes implanted into the anterior nucleus of the thalamus, and vagus nerve stimulator (VNS), the first neurostimulation device approved for epilepsy—have demonstrated a $\geq 50\%$ reduction in seizure frequency in at least 50% of patients. Both VNS and DBS are linked to lower mortality, fewer hospitalizations for status epilepticus, and better Quality of Life (QOL) (15,16).

CONCLUSION:

An imbalance between excitatory and inhibitory neural activity causes recurring seizures, which are a hallmark of epilepsy, a complicated neurological condition. Numerous factors, including genetic, structural, metabolic, infectious, and immunological pathways, are among its causes. Understanding the etiology of this condition has improved due to developments in the roles of neurotransmitters, oxidative stress, and neuronal hyperexcitability. A considerable percentage of patients still have drug-resistant seizures, necessitating surgical, neurostimulatory, or nutritional therapies, even though antiepileptic medications continue to be the first-line treatment. For epileptic patients to have better seizure control and an overall higher quality of life, further research into new therapeutic targets and approaches is necessary.

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